

Connecting the Dots

September 2017

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

During Run 4 the increased luminosity with the consequent increased pile-up will pose significant new challenges for the CMS detector. This is in particular the case for the reconstruction of tracks in the Silicon Tracker and inside showers in the High Granularity Calorimeter. When a charged particle, produced after a collision, flies through the detector, it leaves traces (hits). Tracking is the art of connecting the correct traces recreating particle trajectories. The computation time of a tracking algorithm for reconstructing “which dot belongs to which particle” quickly explodes due to combinatorics. It is furthermore heavily affected by the increased track density expected in the next decade. It is of paramount importance to choose the correct paths to follow and the correct hits to add to the path.

Many track finding algorithms start by building track seeds: groups of two or three hits that are compatible with each other fitting a crude track hypothesis. Compatibility between two hits can also be inferred from hit shapes, akin to footprints, in the CMS Silicon Pixel Tracker. The shape of a hit depends on the energy released in the layer, the crossing angle of the hit at the detector and on the type of particle.

In this project we would like to investigate the use of machine learning techniques for recognizing these hit-shape images. Using these techniques, we hope to reduce the combinatorics and find more stringent compatibility requirements for mitigating the combinatorial explosion. The candidate should take advantage of state of the art machine learning frameworks and libraries for the implementation of these techniques. The candidate will also investigate and explore the applicability of machine learning on different state of the art architectures, in particular many-core architectures such as the Intel Xeon Phi processor. We believe the use of such architectures can greatly accelerate neural-network learning.

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1. Introduction

To study LHC events it is necessary to reconstruct each particle's trajectory. Track reconstruction is a difficult problem due to its combinatorial nature and many fake tracks are generated during the process, most of which are eliminated only after many iterations, increasing the computational cost of the algorithm. In order to avoid part of this cost the objective of this project is to create high quality track seeds, filtering the fake tracks as soon as possible. The filter is implemented with a convolutional neural network which takes hit shapes as the main input features to determine the compatibility between different hits. Several network topologies are trained and tested to study the tradeoff between computational cost, model complexity and model performance. Furthermore, the model inference is benchmarked with several hardware architectures.

2. Cluster Shapes

The first step in track reconstruction is the seed generation, which generates candidate tracks combining hits in the pixel detector. Starting from the inner hit, compatible hits are searched in a small window in the successive layer. The size of the window is determined by predefined parameters. To reduce the number of generated fake tracks we can constrain the seeds using the cluster shapes. Each hit has its own cluster shape which is affected by the energy released by the particle, the crossing angle, and the type of the particle. Using this information, we can use a pattern recognition model to filter track seeds with incompatible hits.

Figure 1. Cluster hit shapes examples.

3. Neural Network

We can model our problem as an image classification task. Given two hit shapes we want to know if they are from the same track or not. Convolutional neural networks are the state of the art in image classification tasks and they have been already applied successfully in particle physics for event classification. For these reasons we decided to use them to solve our pattern recognition problem.

A neural network can be seen as a series of matrix multiplications followed by a nonlinear activation:

$$x = \sigma(Wx + b)$$

in our case the nonlinear activation is a ReLU function:

$$\sigma(x) = \max\{0, x\}$$

A convolutional neural network is a neural network where some layers use the convolution operation. The convolution can be seen as a matrix multiplication where the matrix weights are shared and tied together for each scalar input. Usually convolutional layers are made of three components: a convolution operation, a nonlinear activation, a pooling operation. Only the convolution is mandatory while the other two parts are optional. A 2D discrete convolution can be defined as:

$$y(m, n) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} x(m+i, n+j)w(i, j)$$

The pooling operation instead consider a local area of the input image and outputs one value for each area, depending on the chosen pooling operation. Typical choices include max and average.

4. Data Preparation

The dataset is generated by extracting the generated doublets from CMSSW, available at <http://cms-sw.github.io/>, with events at pileup 35 (which is the number of simultaneous collisions).

For each doublet we saved the global coordinates, positional information regarding the part of the detector where the hit has been generated, the cluster shapes, and some features about the clusters, like the size. The track parameters are also collected and used for analysis.

Looking at the table below we can notice that most of the hit shapes have a low length in both dimensions. In the future it will be possible to reduce the 15x15 hit input shape to improve the computational complexity of our model. Information about the cluster size can still be used by the network if the shape is bigger than the chosen size.

	dim_x_in	dim_y_in	dim_x_out	dim_y_out
mean	2.46	3.58	2.39	2.48
std	2.30	3.39	2.76	2.50
min	1	1	1	1
25%	2	2	1	2
50%	2	2	2	2
75%	3	4	3	3
max	83	143	56	145

The angle between the particle trajectory and the detector's module strongly influence the cluster shape. If the trajectory is almost perpendicular we would expect a small cluster shape, instead small angles can cause longer shapes, because the particle crosses more pixels.

To correct this behaviour we add to the input two separate channels for each hit shape with two angular corrections computed as:

$$\sin - correction = hit \odot \sin\left(\arctan\left(\frac{y}{z}\right)\right)$$

$$\cos - correction = hit \odot \cos\left(\arctan\left(\frac{y}{z}\right)\right)$$

where y and z are the hit's global coordinates and \odot is the elementwise product. These two corrections improve the model performance by considering angular information in the convolutional layers.

Other factors that influence the cluster shape are the layer and module orientation. These problems are treated in different ways in the trained model to test different strategies. The first idea could be to simply ignore these differences in the convolutional part of the network and only pass the flags regarding layer id and module orientation in the feedforward part of the network. This strategy can work in some limited cases, as will be shown in the subsequent chapters. We could also train a different model for each possible mode to ensure that each model is optimized in the best possible way. This is possible but it is expensive since it requires training many different models that will need a different parameter selection and performance analysis. A third solution is to train all the different models together and separating them only at inference time to improve the computational cost of each model. We can add to the input a different channel for each inner and outer layer. For each training sample only the channels corresponding to the inner and outer layer where the doublet's hits reside will contain the cluster shapes, while all the other channels will contain only zeros. The training of this architecture can be done only once for all the different cases and each one will be processed differently because the convolution operation will be different depending on the layers, while the subsequent convolutional kernels will be shared between all the models. At inference time we can separate the models to avoid the additional cost of adding the zero channels for each sample. We are assuming here that one specialized convolutional layer is sufficient and all the other layers can be shared but the same idea can be used to separate other layers.

5. Results and Analysis

The best convolutional network found during the model selection consists of 4 convolutional layers and 3 feedforward layers (with matrix multiplication). Different convolutional architectures have been trained and tested. The models presented in this section represent different solutions, each one with its own advantages and disadvantages.

- **fmap** is a neural network with 4 convolutional layers and 3 feedforward layers. It has been trained with the entire training set using separated feature map for each detector's layer.
- **barbar** has the same architecture as fmap but is trained only with barrel-barrel doublets.
- **barendc** has the same architecture as fmap but is trained only with barrel-endcap doublets.
- **mini_fmap** use a smaller number of layers, two for the convolutional part and 2 for the feedforward part. It is trained with all the training set separating the cluster shapes in different feature maps for each detector's layer.
- **mini_1channel** use the same architecture of mini_fmap but does not separate the cluster shapes in different feature maps.

Figure 1CNN architecture for the doublet filtering model

In the table below we can see the performance metrics for the fmap model and the barrel_only model. We notice that there is no apparent sign of overfitting since the train, validation and test AUC (Area Under the ROC Curve) have close values. Their performance is close and the specialized model doesn't seem to improve much with respect to the general model. This means that we can train a single model for all the data. To guarantee a good event reconstruction we would like to keep most of the true doublets. In the tables, we show the true positive rate (TPR) at different rejection rates. Both models are capable of filtering 75% of the fake doublets data while keeping a TPR > 99%. Since almost all the generated doublets at high levels of pileup are fake this means that we can effectively keep only 25% of the data filtering the doublets.

Table 1. Performance metrics for barrel_only model

train AUC	0.973
val AUC	0.971
test AUC	0.968
bpix1-bpix2	0.971
tpr @ rej 50%	0.998
tpr @ rej 75%	0.992
tpr @ rej 90%	0.941
tpr @ rej 99%	0.376

Table 2. Performance metrics for fmap model

train AUC	0.969
val AUC	0.969
test AUC	0.966
tpr @ rej 50%	0.999
tpr @ rej 75%	0.990
tpr @ rej 90%	0.917
tpr @ rej 99%	0.345
bar-bar AUC	0.952
endc-endc AUC	0.711
bar-endc AUC	0.927
bpix1-bpix2 AUC	0.954

To give a more complete overview of the performance the ROC curve for all the models is plotted below. On the x-axis we have the false positive rate while on the y-axis we have the true positive rate. The x-axis is plotted in a logarithmic scale, since we are mostly interested in high levels of filtering. We can notice a clear performance hit for the smaller models. The barrel-endcap model is also showing much worse performance than the other models. The main problem is that the barrel-endcap doublets are much less than the barrel-barrel case and probably they are not enough to train our model. A bigger dataset could improve the performance in this situation.

A good ROC curve is not enough to guarantee a good performance in our case. The doublets come from tracks generated by different particles and we need a good performance for all of them.

The plots below shows the performance for different models on three different subsets of the data: barrel-barrel, barrel-endcap, endcap-endcap. We can notice a degradation in performance for barrel-endcap and endcap-endcap. This is caused by an insufficient number of samples for these two configurations. A bigger dataset must be used. The feature map model is more affected by this problem since it uses different convolutional kernels in the first layer for the endcap layers, while the single channel model has the same convolution for all the layers. The performance in the endcap-endcap region is unacceptable but it can be easily improved by using different cuts for the endcap region. A higher threshold in the endcap regions would reduce the filtering capability but will maintain a good TPR. Furthermore, the endcap region accounts only for 4.5% of the doublets, and reducing the performance in this area doesn't alter the filter capability too much.

mode	fmap AUC	mini AUC	mini_1channel AUC
all data	0.977	0.967	0.970
bar-bar	0.968	0.953	0.956
bar-endc	0.930	0.884	0.927
endc-endc	0.764	0.720	0.767

6. Hardware and Implementation

Modern architectures exploit parallelism at different levels to achieve the maximum performance. In the past thanks to Moore's law it was possible to write unoptimized programs and obtain improvements with newer hardware. Today it is necessary to design an application to exploit all the different kinds of parallelism in an efficient and scalable way. Modern data centers are often built with heterogeneous components like multicore CPUs, manycore, GPU, FPGA. Each one of these components must be programmed efficiently. In the following paragraphs we give an overview of the possible architectures that can be used to implement neural network inference, their hardware design and their support with software and frameworks.

a. Intel Xeon Phi

Intel Xeon Phi is a many-core processor developed by Intel since 2006 designed for high performance computing. In the current Top500 ranking (<https://www.top500.org/lists/2017/06/>) 3 out of 10 supercomputers use Xeon Phi. The second generation (KNL), can be used standalone booting directly the operating system from the Xeon Phi, while the first generation (KNC) can be used only as a coprocessor. It is based on the Intel Many Integrated Core (MIC) architecture and the instruction set include 512-bit wide vectorization instruction (AVX512), which allows up to 16 single-precision or 8 double precision simultaneous operations.

To achieve the maximum performance from this kind of architecture it is necessary to design an application that exploits all the forms of parallelism present in the architecture. This means using all threads (Xeon Phi Knights Landing features up to 72 cores with 4-way hyperthreading), vectorizing the code, and maximizing local data access.

i. Knights Landing

In our experimental setup we used a Knights Landing (KNL), the second generation of Xeon Phi, to benchmark the inference time for our models. The following benchmark focus only on the inference time because the track reconstruction will be executed in real-time and therefore there are hard constraint on the computational cost that cannot be relaxed. The training instead is executed only once, or possibly multiple times with different model configuration, and does not have any efficiency requirements as long as the time required to complete it does not block the development of the model. The Xeon Phi KNL architecture is built with Intel's 14nm process technology and is made of 36 tiles interconnected by a 2D mesh. Each tile contains 2 cores, for a total of 72 cores, 2 VPU for each core and 1 MB L2 cache shared between pairs of cores. The cores are based on the Atom Silvermont microarchitecture and support out-of-order execution and 4-way hyperthreading. Each VPU include 2 AVX512 units and supports Fused Multiply-Add (FMA) operations. While the first Xeon Phi generation, the Knights Corner (KNC), required the recompilation of the applications, KNL supports legacy code without recompilation. The AVX512 instruction set has been extended with AVX512CD (Conflict Detection), AVX512PF (Prefetch), AVX512ER (Exponential and Reciprocal) instructions. The KNL includes an additional high bandwidth memory (MCDRAM) with 16 GB.

KNL cores are connected with a mesh of rings structure and it is possible to configure three different cluster modes: All-to-All, Quadrant, Sub-NUMA-Clustering. These three modes can be selected at boot time. Additionally, three different modes are available to use the two memories, (DDR and MCDRAM) which can be also selected at boot time: in cache mode the MCDRAM memory is used as another cache level for the DDR memory in a completely transparent way for the application. This is the easiest way because it does not require any change to the application.

Flat mode allows the use of the MCDRAM memory in the same address space of the DDR memory. The application programmer must explicitly specify which data must be allocated on the MCDRAM memory. A third option is the hybrid mode, which allows to use part of the MCDRAM as cache for the DDR memory and part as separate memory in the same address space of the DDR memory. The choice between each mode is a design decision and depends on the application working set size.

ii. Machine Learning on Xeon Phi

It is possible to use Xeon Phi for neural network training and inference. Tensorflow supports Xeon Phi and AVX512 instructions. To enable AVX512 instructions it is necessary to compile Tensorflow using the Math Kernel Library (MKL) as backend. MKL implements math processing routines vectorized and optimized for Intel architectures, like convolution, matrix multiplication, transposition, local response normalization and tensor manipulations.

Since most of the deep learning frameworks are optimized for GPU execution there are some modifications to perform to ensure the best performance on different hardware. For example, convolution input has a (samples, height, width, channels) format by default, while on CPU architectures the (samples, channels, height, width) format has a better data locality and improves performance. This requires a modification in the network definition to ensure the correct format, otherwise MKL will perform the transposition at runtime incurring in additional cost. Several graph optimizations are executed on the computational graph to ensure that the data conversion operations are reduced to a minimum, the Tensorflow operations are substituted with the corresponding MKL optimized version and operations are fused when possible. Other parameters that can increase the performance are the number of threads, which can be controlled with the `OMP_NUM_THREADS` environment variable, the intra-op and inter-op parallelism, which regulates the level of parallelism for each node in the computational graph, the batch size, the transposition for matrix multiplication, and how much time each thread should wait after completing the execution of a task, which can be controlled with `KMP_BLOCKTIME`. Furthermore, Intel announced that in Q4 2017 the new Intel Knights Mill will be released. This is a new Xeon Phi generation optimized for deep learning applications, with new vectorized instructions for low precision operations.

b. FPGA

Another possibility is the usage of FPGA for neural network inference. These kinds of architectures can be optimized only for this specific task, while GPU and manycore are more general architectures. FPGA are interesting for embedded system due to the low power requirements and limited memory size but today they are also used for data centers and large-scale inference, where low power requirements are still important. To limit the data transfer between the FPGA and CPU different quantization techniques are being developed, up to the use of binary weights, which can often give dramatic improvement with only minor accuracy decrease.

One example of this architecture is the Intel Deep Learning Inference Accelerator (DLIA). The user guide can be downloaded from: https://www.intel.com/content/dam/support/us/en/documents/server-products/server-accessories/Intel_DLIA_UserGuide_1.0.pdf

DLIA consist of an Intel Arria 10 FPGA card with a Gen3 x16 PCI express host interface and the software and framework stack used to program and use it. The FPGA is optimized only for inference and cannot be used to train neural networks. The idea is to minimize the price per inference using an FPGA with low power consumption and a good performance. It has a maximum TDP of 60 W and can reach up to 1.5 TFLOPS. DLIA accelerates six common deep learning primitives: convolution, fully connected, concatenation, local response normalization, ReLU, pooling (max and average). The network must be defined in term of this primitives to be executed entirely inside the FPGA. It is also possible to execute the network in hybrid mode, applying some layers outside the FPGA, but this is inefficient because it requires data transfer from the FPGA to the CPU for the input and back to the FPGA for the output, so it should be avoided.

It is possible to use Intel Caffe to run the network on the DLIA accelerator. A new subengine for mklldnn has been defined, MKLDNN:DLA, and to use the accelerator it is sufficient to specify the new engine in the prototxt file that define the network architecture. If some layers are not defined in the Caffe engine they can be executed with a different engine. This hybrid mode has been added to allow the execution of more complex networks with partial support of the accelerator.

An additional tool, **dlia_converter**, can be used to convert a generic prototxt model in a DLIA-compliant model, optimized for execution in the accelerator. For more complex applications, it is possible to use the DLIA with MKLDNN using the C++ API. By default, operations on the DLIA are executed in a lazy way. This allows the possibility to fuse multiple operations together, reducing the amount of memory transfers. There are some limitations in the input, output and convolutional filters dimensions caused by the underlying architectures which are thoroughly described in the user guide. To ensure maximum performance some optimizations must be performed: the batch size must be a multiple of 96, and for maximal throughput it should be the highest multiple of 96 that the host system can handle. The number of threads, regulated with `OMP_NUM_THREADS`, can greatly affect performance. DLIA offers a tool called `find_optimal_openmp_thread_numbers.sh` to find the optimal number of threads for the application. Finally, synchronization between the host system and the accelerator must be avoided, for example by avoiding layers not supported by the accelerator, which require execution on the host.

7. Benchmark

The trained model should be able to filter doublets during the online reconstruction. This means that it should perform inference on doublets generated by each event which arrives in the HLT at a 100 KHz rate. The figure below shows the results of benchmarks executed on two different machines: the first one is a server with a Nvidia GTX1080 Ti GPU, 11 GB of GPU memory, 256 GB of RAM memory, and two Xeon E5-2650 v4 @ 2.20 GHz. The second one has a Nvidia P100 GPU, with 16 GB of GPU memory, 64 GB of main memory, and two Xeon E5-2630 v4 @ 2.20GHz. In both cases we use only the GPU card to execute the inference and we use Tensorflow 1.3. **mini_model** can reach a peak performance of 580000 inferences/sec on the GTX 1080 Ti with a batch size of 16384, while on the P100 it is possible to reach **614000 inferences/sec** with a batch size of 8192. **fmap_model** reach a peak performance of **110000 inferences/sec** with a bath size of 2048. After these maximum points we notice a degradation of the performance.

Table 4. Inference performance computed as samples/sec against the batch size.

These plots do not include the performance for Xeon Phi. Unfortunately, our efforts to configure Tensorflow with the AVX512 instructions failed, and the Intel documentation to setup Tensorflow for Xeon Phi was at the time of writing incomplete and did not include detailed instruction to compile Tensorflow with AVX512 support, which is essential to guarantee maximum performance on the **Xeon Phi** architecture. Nonetheless, we benchmarked the inference with an unoptimized Tensorflow CPU version, reaching a peak of about **26'000 inferences/sec** with the mini_model. A similar test was performed on a server with 256 GB of RAM memory and two **Xeon E5** (E5-2640v4 @ 2.40GHz), a model with 10 cores and 2-way hyperthreading. With this configuration the inference achieves a peak performance of **121'000 inferences/sec** in the same conditions. The Xeon E5 configuration is about 5 times slower than the Nvidia P100 while the Xeon Phi is 20 times slower. It must be noted that Tensorflow is optimized for GPU architectures and big models that can use all the GPU memory with much smaller batch sizes. Furthermore, using the Nvidia profiler nvprof we have seen that about 30% of the computational time is spent moving to and from the GPU memory. Our benchmark transfers each sample from main memory to the GPU memory, but this could be avoided in principle since the track seeding can run entirely on GPU. We are not considering the cost to create the additional feature maps with the angular correction. These could be computed on the GPU in parallel given the original cluster shapes and the additional features and their computation is an additional cost at inference time.

To give an idea of the difference in performance between the Nvidia GTX 1080 Ti and the Intel Xeon Phi we plotted in the figure below the inferences per second against the batch size, in a logarithmic scale for both axes. We can see that the performance is up to 20 times slower.

Figure 3. Inference performance comparison between Nvidia GTX 1080 Ti and Intel Xeon Phi.

To test Xeon Phi with a different framework, we used Intel Caffe, an Intel optimized version of Caffe. We installed the framework using the script available at <https://github.com/WalteRiviera/wizard> and converted the network to the corresponding prototxt format, the language used by Caffe to specify the network architecture. This version support MKLDNN and is optimized for execution on Xeon Phi. The figure below shows the results of this benchmark. A maximum throughput of 45500 samples/second is reached with a batch size of 8192. This is an improvement against the 26000 that was achieved with Tensorflow but still far from the results obtained with both GPUs.

Figure 4. Performance of Xeon Phi using Caffe for inference with mini_model.

8. Technical Problems

Several technical problems have been encountered during the benchmarking phase. These problems are highlighted in this section

a. Tensorflow for Xeon Phi

According to the Intel site, Tensorflow currently supports Xeon Phi and AVX512 instructions, and there are various considerations to take into account to maximize the performance, which can be found at <https://software.intel.com/en-us/articles/tensorflow-optimizations-on-modern-intel-architecture>.

Unfortunately, I did not find any official source that explained how to compile Tensorflow to enable AVX512 instructions. After compiling with the following instruction:

```
bazel build --config=mkl --copt="-DEIGEN_USE_VML" -s -c opt
//tensorflow/tools/pip_package:build_pip_package
```

Tensorflow continued to issue the following warning:

```
tensorflow/core/platform/cpu_feature_guard.cc:45] The TensorFlow library wasn't
compiled to use AVX512F instructions, but these are available on your machine and
could speed up CPU computations.
```

Furthermore, the same python script used for testing the network, which was used for all the previous Tensorflow benchmark, failed during the network execution without giving any useful error message. The import command:

```
import tensorflow as tf
```

was successful, but the inference command:

```
session.run(...)
```

crashed the process. I was not able to find the cause of the problem.

b. Caffe for DLIA

After the initial installation and configuration of the DLIA software, I converted the same topology used with Tensorflow into a prototxt file to use it with Caffe. The network was successfully tested on my local machine, with a Windows operating system and the standard Caffe distribution. The same network did not work with the Intel Caffe shipped with the DLIA software package. The process became unresponsive before starting any computation during the prototxt loading, and could be stopped only with a SIGKILL signal. These were the last output lines:

```
layer {
  name: "loss"
  type: "SoftmaxWithLoss"
  bottom: "fc8"
```



```

    bottom: "label"

    top: "loss"
}

I0828 16:04:19.016451 22987 layer_factory.hpp:114] Creating layer data
I0828 16:04:19.016718 22987 net.cpp:218] Creating Layer data
I0828 16:04:19.016733 22987 net.cpp:871] data -> data
I0828 16:04:19.016747 22987 net.cpp:871] data -> label

```

The DLIA examples in the 'object_recognition' folder worked without problems, but did not use Caffe tools, only the prototxt file to define the network topology.

After this failed attempt, I tried to compile Intel Caffe from scratch. Unfortunately, the Intel Caffe on github did not support the DLIA.

After several failed attempts, I was successful using the script found at <https://github.com/WalteRiviera/wizard>. With this version, a problem with the concatenation layer made the test fail, and we had to change the engine only for that specific layer to avoid the problem. I was not able to test the DLIA with this version since it was not supported.

9. Conclusion

Track reconstruction is one of the most expensive steps performed in the High Level Trigger, and it will suffer from the pileup increase due to the High Luminosity LHC. The doublet filtering approach that we explored in this project can be used to improve the computational cost of the algorithm and reduce the detrimental effect caused by the pileup increase. The current model is capable of filtering fake doublets while keeping a good efficiency. Further studies are necessary to integrate the model into the CMSSW and understand the performance of the final reconstruction using this filter.

Additionally, we developed some preliminary benchmark to evaluate the inference cost. Several attempts are currently being developed to reduce the cost for large-scale inference, using both software and hardware solutions. In the future, it will be interesting to test the model with more mature tools, for example the Intel DLIA, to evaluate the network computational cost with hardware optimized for neural network inference.

